

Efficacy of Financial Therapy Intervention on Financial Stress and Mental Well-Being of Families in Yenagoa Metropolis

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Abstract

The study evaluates the efficacy of a seven week Financial Therapy (FT) intervention on financial stress and mental well-being of families in Yenagoa metropolis, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Three objectives were stated and three hypotheses tested at 0.05 significant level. Sample consisted of 60 breadwinners of families drawn through convenience sampling. Three stages were used in collecting data: pre-treatment, treatment and post-treatment. Quasi-experimental design was adopted for the study. Four instruments were used, namely, the Klontz Money Script Inventory (KMSI-R) by Klontz, Britt, Mentzer & Klontz (2011), the Money Attitude Scale (MAS) by Yamauchi and Templer (1982), Beck Hopelessness Scale (BHS) developed by Beck, Weisman, Lester and Trexter (1994), and the Symptoms Checklist Scale -90-R developed by Derogatis (1994). Reliability of the instruments was established through test-retest; coefficients obtained were: KMIS-R = 0.68; MAS = 0.73; Beck Hopelessness Scale = 0.72, Symptoms Checklist-90-R = 0.80. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean) for hypothesis one and t-test of independent samples at the .05 level of significance to test hypotheses two and three. Results obtained revealed that FT intervention has significant effect on reduction of financial stress and enhancement of well-being of breadwinners of families in Yenagoa metropolis, financial and educational status of breadwinners have significant effect on the efficacy of FT intervention. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that, employers of labour should provide financial counselling services for employees intermittently to reduce the effect of economic pressures on individuals and households and that the state Government should establish State counselling centres manned by Professional Counsellors to provide counselling services.

Keywords: Efficacy, Financial Therapy, Financial Stress, Mental Well-being, and Professional Counsellors.

Introduction

Recent happenings, incidences and experiences in Yenagoa and reports across Nigeria reveal increased cases of hardship resulting in untold suffering faced by families. Recent reports also reveal increased incidences of crime, criminality, violence, health issues such as sudden slumping resulting in other conditions like high blood pressure, strokes and deaths. These situations may not be unconnected with the increased stress people experience as a result of hardship in the land attributed to the removal of petroleum subsidy resulting in increased cost of living and many families finding it difficult to provide basic needs. To worsen the situation, prices of goods escalate on daily bases without any increase in means of livelihood. The present normal in Nigeria can

induce undue stress on families resulting in a myriad of complication including physical, psychological and mental issues.

Hardship is severe suffering or privation, difficult or unpleasant conditions of life. Hardship is a condition of life that causes difficulty or suffering for example being without a job or enough money as is the experience of many persons in the country. It is a condition that is difficult to endure. Hardship can be financial, economic and otherwise. Economic hardship, as defined in Treasury Regulations and the Internal Revenue Manual, occurs when, an individual is 'unable to pay his or her reasonable basic living expenses'. It refers to the difficulties faced by individuals or families due to loss of income, unemployment, job instability, and economic insecurity. The level of hardship in the Nigerian economy is high because there is serious underemployment and unemployment in the country, leading to reduced purchasing power that does not match the inflation rate ignited by the removal of oil subsidies by the Bola Ahmed Tinubu administration.

Financial hardship refers to the inability to meet basic living expenses. It is the inability to provide basic daily needs or requirements. It is an unplanned, unforeseen financial expense that is beyond a person's ability to manage. The inability of a person to meet basic living expenses can result in anxiety, anger, frustration, depression and the like. Hardship in Yenagoa has resulted in many families being unable to cater for basic needs such as food, shelter, clothing, and education. Many families can no longer pay other necessary bills, or manage their health challenges as the price of drugs escalate on daily bases. Due to the hardship, many persons have resorted to begging and owing debts. Many creditors no longer give credit facilities to some persons any more due to their inability to repay while some who resort to begging receive insults, abuses, embarrassment, humiliation, arrests, threats, assault and even imprisonment. These unpleasant experiences have led to increased psychological, emotional, mental and other health conditions as a result of financial stress imposed by hardship.

Financial stress is emotional tension that is specially related to money. Anyone can experience financial stress, but financial stress occurs mostly in households with low incomes. The stress can result from not making enough money to meet needs such as paying rent, paying bills, buying groceries etc. People with less income might experience additional stress due to their jobs. Their jobs might lack flexibility when it comes to taking time off. They might work in unsafe environments, but they are afraid to leave because they would not be able to support themselves financially while they look for another job. People with low or no income may not have access to resources to manage their financial stress, either, such as health insurance to receive support or treatment. When financial stress is severe, people experience negative effects on their mental health and wellbeing. Financial stress can lead to anxiety, depression, behavioural changes like withdrawing from social activities, or physical symptoms like stomach aches or headaches (Zeamer, 2021, Fernandes, Lynch & Netemeyer, 2014).

World Health Organization (2012) defined mental health as 'a state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stress of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to his or her community'. Mental health is how one feels about oneself and others, able to meet the demands of life and to develop psychologically and emotionally. Being mentally healthy is having the strength to overcome the difficulties and challenges the person can face at times, to have confidence and self-esteem, to be able to take decisions and to believe in oneself (Grasso, 2017). Mental health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being. Mental health includes emotional, psychological and social well-being. It affects how a person thinks, feels, and acts. It also helps determine how one handles

stress, relate to others, and make choices. Mental health is important at every stage of life, from childhood and adolescence through adulthood. It is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease (WHO, 2012).

Audu, Mshella, Mburza, & Maina (2017) and Gee (2011) opined that feelings of well-being are fundamental to the overall health of an individual, enabling one to successfully overcome difficulties and achieve what one wants out of life. Past experiences, attitudes and outlook can all impact well-being as can physical or emotional trauma following specific events. Hence mental well-being affects the extent to which one can perform a task and how successful. The state of one's mental health determines how well a person also adjusts to situations. It is a state of well-being in which a person realizes personal abilities, can work efficiently and can compete with normal stresses in life (WHO, 2012).

From the foregoing, it is obvious that there is the need to help people explore their emotional and psychological relationship with their finances. This is not unconnected with the fact that it may be possible that some persons are not able to manage their finances properly. People need to be educated on how to manage financial stress and cope with the present realities to ensure wellbeing. Hence, the need for financial therapy.

Financial therapy is a specialized type of therapy that requires certification from an organization (Xiao, Lawrence & Francis, 2014)). The Financial Therapy Association defines financial therapy as 'a process informed by both therapeutic and financial competences that helps people think, feel, communicate and behave differently to improve overall well-being through evidence-based practices and interventions'. It combines financial advice and emotional support to help manage financial stress. Worry about money and financial matters can have a crippling effect on people, negatively impacting their personal life, family life, work, and all other aspects of their lives.

The field of financial therapy came to limelight in the aftermath of great recession of 2007-2008, although its roots go back to the 1990s when researchers began to look more closely at the psychological and emotional aspects of money. The goal of financial therapy is to instil in people a positive attitude about their finances, which is the first step in setting and achieving financial goals. This is hinged on the belief that when people change their perspective about money from negative to positive, they are more likely to think and behave in ways that allow them to build real wealth and manage their lives, and make right decisions no matter what life throws at them. A survey conducted by financial services firm, Capital One found that as of 2019, finances were the number one source of stress cited by 73% of survey respondents. People reported worrying about their finances more than politics (59%), work (49%), or family (46%). In the Capital One survey, finance-related stress was especially common among those in Generation Z (82%) and Millennials (81%).

Studies by Danes, Rodriguez and Brewton (2013), Zeamer (2021), Hawkins and Zuiker (2019) and Richards and Seedhouse (2016), Durband, Carlson and Stueve (2019) and Wliis (2008) revealed the effectiveness of financial therapy in reducing financial stress and enhancing wellbeing among various populations. Pulvino and Pulvino (2010) and Theodos, Simms, Treskon, Stacy, Brash, Emam, and Collazos (2015) investigated communication skills for financial professionals and found positive impact of financial counselling on improvement of communication skills.

To this end, it is obvious that financial hardships, especially without good financial knowledge and support, can be incredibly stressful and lead to anxiety and depression. Financial therapy, combining thorough financial planning with several aspects of psychological counseling, offers a promising solution to many of these challenges. By addressing both the practical and emotional

aspects of financial decision-making, financial therapy interventions aimed to improve financial behaviours, reduce financial stress, and enhance overall mental well-being. However, the efficacy of such interventions in the Nigerian context, particularly in Yenagoa Metropolis, remains underexplored. This study sought to examine the impact of financial therapy on financial stress and mental well-being among families in Yenagoa, providing empirical knowledge into its effectiveness as a strategy for promoting financial stability and psychological resilience in Bayelsa State and Nigeria at large.

Statement of the Problem

Money plays a large role in a person's overall well-being, and the stresses of managing money and dealing with financial pitfalls can take a huge toll on one's emotional and mental health. If left uncontrolled, this burden can spread into other areas of a person's life. In many cases behavioural issues cause a person to adapt unhealthy financial routines including unhealthy spending or excessive worry when the available money is grossly inadequate to cater for needs, especially basic needs. Unhealthy financial routines such as excessive eating, drinking, impulsive buying, celebration of birthdays or other elaborate ceremonies can impose undue financial stress leading to excessive worrying as some persons even resort to owing debts and borrowing to maintain their unhealthy financial routine. Excessive worry imposes undue emotional stress which leads to anxiety and other behavioural and health complications such as depression, alcoholism, violent behaviours, divorce, school dropout, mental issues, suicide attempts and suicide, high blood pressure, strokes, slumping and dying etc.

Based on the foregoing, people, especially lower income households need to be educated on how to manage current expenses, build savings, make plans to pay off debts, and navigate public assistance benefits. Every household need to be equipped with core concepts such as money management which includes understanding their options regarding debts which are priorities, develop budgets and money plans, understand the pros and cons of different options, manage financial concerns and general money habits and practices that are essential life skills. When people are able to manage their financial concerns, it will result in reduced stress and will enhance well-being.

In the light of the present situation of economic hardship in Nigeria which is imposing undue stress on people resulting in many cases of crises in families, there is the need to carry out research on how to assist people manage available resources and reduce stress to promote mental well-being. It is the thinking of the researcher that financial therapy could assist in reduction and management of financial stress on families and enhance their well-being. The research is carried out to provide empirical data on the efficacy of financial therapy on financial stress and mental wellbeing of families in Yenagoa metropolis.

Objectives of the study

The following objectives were designed to guide the study:

1. To find out the effect of financial therapy intervention on financial stress and well-being of breadwinners of families in Yenagoa Metropolis.
2. To find out the effect of financial status on efficacy of financial therapy intervention in Yenagoa metropolis.
3. To find out the effect of educational status on efficacy of financial therapy intervention in Yenagoa metropolis.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested in this study:

HO₁: FT intervention has no significant effect on financial stress and well-being of breadwinners of families in Yenagoa Metropolis.

HO₂: Financial status has no significant effect on the efficacy of financial therapy intervention on breadwinners of families in Yenagoa metropolis.

HO₃: Educational status has no significant effect on the efficacy of financial therapy intervention on breadwinners of families in Yenagoa Metropolis.

Methodology

Quasi experimental design was adopted for the study. Quasi experimental design is relevant because it is an empirical study used to estimate the causal impact of an intervention on its target population with random assignment. With random assignment, study participants have the same chance of being assigned to the intervention group or the comparison group. As a result, differences between groups on both observed and unobserved characteristics would be due to chance, rather than to a systematic factor related to treatment which is the concern of the present study (Grasso, 2017).

The target population for the study comprised all breadwinners of families in Yenagoa metropolis. This population was chosen because all families have breadwinners and are also experiencing the present hardship in Yenagoa due to rapid increase in the cost of living. A sample of 120 breadwinners of families were selected from the population through convenience sampling. Sixty breadwinners were assigned to experimental group and the other sixty to control group through randomization using odd and even numbers.

Four instruments were used for the study, namely, the Klontz Money Script Inventory (KMSI) by Klontz, Britt, Mentzer and Klontz (2011), the Money Attitude Scale (MAS) by Yamauchi and Templer (1982), Beck Hopelessness Scale (BHS) developed by Beck, Weisman, Lester and Trexter (1994), and the Symptoms Checklist Scale -90-R developed by Derogatis (1994). The KMSI-R made up of 45 items is for identification of belief and behavioural patterns that may prove to be detrimental but are not initially evident to the therapist or client; the MAS consisted of 29 items measuring money as a tool of power, budgeting/retaining money, anxiety regarding money and obsession; (BHS) consisted of 20 items intended to measure the severity of negative attitudes about the future. This scale was used to assess the extent of hopelessness and has been shown to be predictive of suicide risk (Santos, Matos and Machado, 2016). It contains 30 items tapping the appraisal and expression of emotions in self and others, regulation of emotion in self and others, and utilization of emotions in solving problems; the Symptoms Checklist-90-R is an instrument widely used to assess both domain-specific (for example, anxiety, psychosis) and broad levels of individual distress. The global index of the Symptom Checklist-90-R was selected for analyses so that changes in general levels of distress could be assessed at pre-treatment and post-treatment phases.

Items on the four instruments were presented as statements to which respondents were instructed to indicate their levels of agreement or disagreement on a 4-point scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) weighted 4 points, 3 points, 2 points and 1 point respectively. All the four instruments were adapted for the study.

The study was conducted in three phases which were pretest, treatment and posttest phases.

Treatment consisted of training sessions. The training focused on enhancing clients' capabilities by teaching them behavioural skills and this was carried out within 7 weeks (1 hour weekly) Group therapy was carried out as follows:

Sessions	Training
Week One	General Introduction; Sharing Experiences; Understanding which debts are priorities.
Week Two	Develop budget and money plans effectively; Understand the pros and cons of different options to manage financial issues.
Week Three	Understand their rights and access to help; Access to grants or concessions; Negotiate with creditors; Access dispute resolution services.
Week Four	Interpersonal Effectiveness; Problem solving; Distress tolerance.
Week Five	Emotion Regulation; Identify and Label Emotions, Identify obstacles to changing emotions, Reduce vulnerability to emotion mind, Increase positive emotion events.
Week Six	Emotion Regulation; Increase mindfulness to current emotions, Take opposite action, Apply distress tolerance.
Week Seven	Wrap up, review, establish new targets, post-assessment.

Note: Sessions were held in groups at times convenient for the group. Individual sessions were arranged for participants with issues of time constraint.

To ascertain validity, a draft of the instruments was given to three (3) Counsellors and Experts in Test Measurement and Evaluation from Niger Delta University, Amassoma and University of Africa, Toru Orua for vetting. All corrections and modifications made were effected, making the instrument valid for the study. The reliability of the four instruments was determined through the test re-test method for a measure of stability of the instruments. Stratified random sampling was used to draw a sample of 20 breadwinners of families from the population not used for the study. Copies of the instruments were administered to the sample. After an interval of three weeks, the same instruments were administered to the same sample. The initial and the re-test scores were correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. The reliability of the KMIS-R = 0.68; MAS = 0.73; Beck Hopelessness Scale = 0.72, Symptoms Checklist-90-R = 0.80. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics for hypothesis one and t-test of independent samples at the .05 level of significance to test hypotheses two and three.

Results

HO₁: FT intervention has no significant effect on financial stress and well-being of breadwinners of families in Yenagoa Metropolis.

Table 1: ANOVA on effect of FT intervention on financial stress and well-being of Breadwinners of families in Yenagoa Metropolis.

Pre-test			
FT	N	X	SD
Exp. group	60	59.3655	14.7127
Control group	60	93.0666	12.5768

Post-test			
FT	N	X	SD
Exp. group	60	75.5564	11.8319
Control group	60	92.3446	13.0023

Table 1 shows that the mean score of the experimental group in pre-test was 59.3655 while the mean score of the post-test was 75.5564. This indicates a significant increase in the mean score of the post test of the experimental group which implies that FT intervention had significant effect on financial stress and well-being of breadwinners of families in Yenagoa metropolis. Therefore, hypothesis 1 which states that FT intervention has no significant effect on financial stress and well-being of breadwinners of families in Yenagoa metropolis was rejected.

HO₂: Financial status has no significant effect on the efficacy of financial therapy intervention on breadwinners of families in Yenagoa metropolis.

Table 2: t-test of independent samples on effect of financial status on the efficacy of financial therapy intervention on breadwinners of families in Yenagoa metropolis.

Fin. Status	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Result
HIGH	32	68.35	15.62	118	3.45	1.96	Sig.
LOW	88	86.23	9.66				

Table 2 showed that the t-cal value of 3.45 was greater than the t-crit value of 1.96 at 0.5 alpha level, indicating that financial status of breadwinners has significant effect on the efficacy of FT intervention. Therefore hypothesis 2 was rejected.

HO₃: Educational status has no significant effect on the efficacy of financial therapy intervention on breadwinners of families in Yenagoa Metropolis.

Table 3: t-test of independent samples on effect of educational status on the efficacy of financial therapy intervention on breadwinners of families in Yenagoa metropolis.

Edu. Status	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Result
Undergraduates	43	57.68	13.06	59	2.87	1.96	Sig.
Graduates	77	96.9	12.22				

Table 3 showed that the t-cal value of 2.87 was greater than the t-crit value of 1.96 at 0.5 alpha level, indicating that educational status of breadwinners has significant effect on the efficacy of FT intervention. Therefore hypothesis 3 was rejected.

Summary of Finding

The finding of the study is summarized below:

1. FT intervention has significant effect on financial stress and well-being of breadwinners of families in Yenagoa metropolis.
2. Financial status of breadwinners has significant effect on the efficacy of FT intervention.
3. Educational status of breadwinners has significant effect on the efficacy of FT intervention.

Discussion

The study investigated the efficacy of financial therapy intervention on financial stress and mental well-being of families in Yenagoa metropolis. The first finding of the study revealed that FT intervention has significant effect on reduction of financial stress and enhancement of well-being of breadwinners of families in Yenagoa metropolis. Therefore hypothesis 1 was rejected. The finding is in agreement with the finding of Zeamer (2021) and Archuleta and Grable (2011) who conducted studies on the effect of financial counselling on clients with financial management problems in Raleigh, North Carolina, USA. They carried out six financial counselling sessions which were between 1 hour, 34 minutes, and 45 minutes long, with most sessions being a little over an hour. The focus group was 43 minutes long and found that clients gained some clarity and increased confidence, knowledge and financial independence. Also congruent with the finding of the present study is the finding of Delgadillo and Britt (2015) who carried out a study on financial coaching and financial therapy on well-being. Participants reported reduced depressive symptoms, hopelessness, and psychiatric distress and reported increased social adjustment from pre-treatment to post-treatment as changes were confirmed through follow-up after eight weeks suggesting that financial coaching and therapy has significant effect on participants. The finding of the study is also congruent with Iverson, Cradus, Renct, Suvak, and Smith, (2011), Iverson, Shek and Fruzzetti (2016) and Theodos et al. (2015) who conducted a research on the cognitive behavior therapy and effect of dialectical behaviour therapy on victims of domestic abuse respectively and found that DBT has significant effect on wellness and adjustment of female victims. Audu et al. (2017) investigated the Effect of Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy on Emotional Intelligence among internally displaced women in Dalori internally displaced person's camp, Maiduguri, Borno State and found that RET was effective in improving the emotional intelligence of internally displaced persons. The similarity in the findings with the present study may be attributed to effectiveness of therapeutic interventions in matters relating to general well-being and also the fact that many persons who need financial therapy actually yearn for help which they can hardly find or receive without spending money.

The second finding revealed that financial status of breadwinners has significant effect on the efficacy of FT intervention. Therefore, hypothesis two was rejected. The finding is in tandem with the finding of Hastings, Madrian and Skimmyhorn (2013) and Fox, Bartholomew and Lee (2005) who conducted a study on impact of Financial Counselling on financial literacy, financial education and financial outcomes. Results of the study indicated that the t-cal of 3.56 was significant at .01 level which implies that difference in financial literacy, financial education and status had significant effect on the effectiveness of FT on financial outcomes of participants. The finding of the present study also aligns with the position of Wagner (2019) study on financial education and financial literacy by income and education groups which revealed that financial education and financial status significantly influenced participants' levels of comprehension of content.

The third finding revealed that educational status of breadwinners has significant effect on the efficacy of FT intervention. Therefore, hypothesis three was rejected. The finding is in tandem with the finding of Crespo and Arinero (2010) who carried out a study on assessment of efficacy of psychological treatment for women victims of violence by their intimate partners and found that educational status has significant effect. Also, Cunha and Conclaves (2015) study on the efficacy of assessment of an intervention programme with batterers found significant effect of educational status on effectiveness of the programme. The finding is also congruent with the finding of Teibowei (2018) who conducted a study on the Effectiveness of DBT intervention programme on female victims of spousal abuse in Bayelsa State and found that that educational level had significant effect on effectiveness of DBT intervention programme on female victims of spousal abuse in Bayelsa State with t-value of 14.42 at 0.5 level of significance for a two-tailed test. The similarity in result may be attributed to the fact that the more educated people are, the better understanding they may have about items on the instruments; they may also receive more exposure, and may acquire more social skills which help them manage and cope with stressors.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that FT intervention is effective in reduction of financial stress and enhancement of well-being of breadwinners of families in Yenagoa Metropolis, Bayelsa State. Financial status and educational status also had significant effect on the efficacy of FT intervention on financial stress and mental well-being of breadwinners of families in Yenagoa metropolis, Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. FT is effective in reducing financial stress. Therefore, it is recommended that employers of labour should provide financial counselling services for employees intermittently to reduce the effect of economic pressures on individuals and households.
2. Civil Society Organizations, Non - Governmental Organizations and Counselling Association of Nigeria should liaise with Bayelsa State Government to establish State Counselling centres manned by Professional Counsellors to provide counselling services in all Local Government Areas.
3. Counselling Association of Nigeria should liaise with Bayelsa State Ministry of Information and Orientation to, in conjunction with National Orientation Agency, carryout enlightenment programmes on the need for free adult education programmes to provide platforms for uneducated adults to receive formal education.

References

- Achuleta, K. L., & Grable, J. E. (2011). The future of financial planning and counselling: An introduction to financial therapy. In J. E. Grable, K. L. Archuleta, & R. R. Nazarinia (Eds.), *Financial planning and counselling scales* (pp. 33–59). Springer Publishing.
- Audu, A., Mshella, B., Mburza, N. R. & Maina, A. K. (2017). Effect of Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy on Emotional Intelligence among internally displaced women in Dalori internally displaced person's camp, Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria. *The Counsellor*, 36(2), 72-81.

- Beck, A. T., Weisman, A., Lester, D., & Trexter, L. (1994). The Measurement of Pessimism: The Hopelessness Scale. *Journal Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 42, 861-865.
- Crespo, M. & Arinero, M. (2010). Assessment of efficacy of a psychological treatment for woman victims of violence by their intimate partners. *The Spanish Journal of Psychology*, 13, 854-859.
- Cunha, O. & Conclaves, R. A. (2015). The efficacy assessment of an intervention programme with batterers. *Small Group Research*, 46, 458-472.
- Danes, S. M., Rodriguez, M. C. & Brewton, K. E. (2013). Learning context when studying financial planning in high schools: Nesting of student, teacher, and class- room characteristics. *Journal of Financial Counseling and Planning*, 24(2), 20-36.
- Delgadillo, L. M. & Britt, S. L. (2015). Financial coaching and financial therapy: Differences and boundaries. *Family and Consumer Sciences Research Journal*, 44(1), 63-72. <https://doi:10.1111/fcsr.12078>
- Derogatis, L. R. (1994). Symptom checklist-90-R (SC90-R). Administration, Scoring, and Procedures Manual (3rd ed). Minneapolis, MN: National Computer Systems.
- Durband, D. B., Carlson, M. B. & Stueve, C. (2019). The financial counselling profession. In D. Durband, R. Law, & A. Mazzolini (Eds.), *Financial Counselling*, pp. 1-16. New York: Springer.
- Fernandez, D., Lynch, J. G., Jr. & Netemeyer, R. G. (2014). Financial literacy, financial education, and downstream financial behaviours. *Management Science*, 60(8), 1861-1883. <https://doi:10.1287/mnsc.2013.1849>
- Fox, J., Bartholomew, S. & Lee, J. (2005). Building the case for financial education. *Journal of Consumer Affairs*, 39(1), 195-214. doi:10.1111/j.1745-6606.2005.00009.x
- Gee, J. P. (2011). An introduction to discourse analysis: Theory and method. Oxfordshire: Routledge.
- Grasso, A. (2017). Emotion regulation in everyday life. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 15, 34-38.
- Hastings, J. S., Madrian, B. C. & Skimmyhorn, W. L. (2013). Financial literacy, financial education and financial outcomes. *Annual Review of Economics*, 5, 347-373.
- Hawkins, B. P. & Zuiker, V. S. (2019). Financial counsellors' experiences working with clients of color: Lessons of cultural awareness. *Journal of Financial Counselling and Planning*, 30(1), 6-17. <https://doi:10.1891/1052-3073.30.1.6>
- Klontz, B., Britt, S. L., Mentzer, J. & Klontz, T. (2011). Money Beliefs and Financial Behaviours: Development of the Klontz Money Script Inventory. *The Journal of Financial Therapy, Vol. 2, Issue 1*, 1 - 22.
- Iverson, K., Cradus, J., Renct, P., Suvak, M. & Smith, K. (2011). Cognitive behaviour therapy and post-traumatic stress disorder and depression symptoms reduces risk for future Intimate partner violence among interpersonal trauma survivors. *Journal of Consulting*, 21, 212-215.
- Iverson, K., Sheck, C. & Fruzzetti, A. (2016). Dialectic behaviour therapy for woman victims of domestic abuse. A pilot study. *Professional Psychology Research and Practice*, 40, 242-248.
- Pulvino, C. J. & Pulvino, C. A. (2010). Financial counselling: A strategic approach: Communication skills for financial professionals. Instructional Enterprises.
- Richards, K. & Seedhouse, P. (2016). *Applying conversation analysis*. New York: Springer.
- Santos, A., Matos, M. & Machado, A. (2016). Effectiveness of a group intervention programmes for female victims of intimate partner violence. *SAGE Journals*: Sagepub.com.

- Teibowei, B. J. (2018). Effectiveness of Dialectical Behaviour Therapy (DBT) intervention programme for female victims of spousal abuse in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. *Prestige Journal of Counselling, Vol. 1, No. 1, 13 – 24.*
- Theodos, B., Simms, M., Treskon, M., Stacy, C., Brash, R., Emam, D. & Collazos, J. (2015). *An evaluation of the impacts and implementation approaches of financial coaching programs.* Washington, DC: Urban Institute.
- Wagner, J. (2019). Financial education and financial literacy by income and education groups. *Journal of Financial Counselling and Planning, 30(1), 132–141.* <https://doi:10.1891/1052-3073.30.1.132>
- World Health Organization (2017). Fact Sheets on Spousal Abuse. Global Health Observatory Publication. WHO (<https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/978924012455>).
- Willis, L. E. (2008). Against financial-literacy education. *Iowa Law Review, 94(1), 197–286.*
- Xiao, J. J., Lawrence, F. & Francis, A. (2014). Financial counseling: Categorizing research papers published in journal of financial counselling and planning. In V. J. Mason (Ed.), *Proceedings of the association for financial counseling and planning education* (pp. 4–7). Retrieved from [https:// www.researchgate.net/publication/271271126_Financial_Counselling_Catego](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/271271126_Financial_Counselling_Catego)
- Yamauchi, K. T., & Templer, D. J. (1982). The development of a money attitude scale. *Journal of Personality Assessment, 46 (5), 522 – 528.*
- Zeamer, C. A. (2021). Using Discourse Analysis to Evaluate the Effectiveness of Financial Counselling. *Journal of Financial Counselling and Planning, Volume 32, Number 1, 2021, 330-3.*